

**A DECADAL ANALYSIS OF LANDUSE PATTERNS BEFORE AND
AFTER THE CONSTRUCTION OF ZOBE DAM IN DUTSIN-MA LGA, KATSINA
STATE**

BY

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**A RESEARCH PROJECT SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF GEOGRAPHY,
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DECLARATION

I declare that the work in the project entitled “**A decadal analysis of landuse patterns before and after the construction of Zobe dam in Dutsin-ma LGA, Katsina State**” has been performed by me in the Department of Geography, Faculty of Earth and Environmental Science. The information derived from the literature has been duly acknowledged in the context and a list of references provided. No part of this research was previously presented for another degree at this or any other institution.

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SOC/2019/11385

Signature and Date

CERTIFICATION

This project entitled “**A decadal analysis of landuse patterns before and after the construction of Zobe dam in Dutsin-ma LGA, Katsina State**” meets the regulations governing the award of (Bachelor Degree) in the Department of Geography, Faculty of Earth and Environmental science of the Federal University Dutsin-ma, Katsina State. And is approved for its contribution to knowledge and literary presentation.

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DEDICATION

This research project is dedicated to my beloved parents, my father Alhaji Yahaya Abdu Gama and my mother Hajiya Amina Musa Ibrahim for investing their resources in my studies, which in turn have brought me to where I am today.

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All praises and gratitude's due to Almighty ALLAH (S.W.T) the most beneficent and the most merciful who has guided, protected and given me the opportunity of reaching this height. May His blessing be upon the gentle soul of the noble Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W) His households, companions and generality of the ummah who follows His footsteps amen. I am so grateful to my supervisor Dr Christopher Ndabula for guiding me so helpfully along the long journey towards completing this research who works day and night, dedicates his time and energy to go through my work several times and offer valuable suggestions, advice and guidance at every step of this work may ALLAH (S.W.T) bless him abundantly, amen. My special appreciation to the Head of Department Dr I.B. Abaje. Thanks also to my project coordinator Ms W.M. Ibrahim and the entire lecturers of the department of Geography, Federal University, Dutsin-ma, Katsina State. My special gratitude also extended to the most important people in my life, my beloved parents, who fortified the pillar of this product by their support, prayers, consistent and ceaseless encouragement through my entire life and through this program, ensuring I was never in want. God would forever reward you for the love that you have lavished on me. Special thanks also to my brothers and sisters whose names are enormous enough to be mention individually. My appreciation also goes to my friend and brother, Abubakar Umar Radda, for his immense contribution in the cause of my study. My appreciation to the Department of Geography, Faculty of Earth and Environmental Science and Federal University, Dutsin-ma, Katsina State at large.

ABSTRACT

This study covers the landuse patterns on the land Before and after the construction of Zobe Dam. The Dam in question is located along the Karaduwa river, which is a sub-basin of the Sokoto Rima basin. The objectives of the research were to identify and map out the landuse patterns before and after the construction of the dam, to assess the extents of the landuse on decadal basis, and to examine the status of landuse that have recorded loss or gains in extent. Multi-temporal Landsat satellite imageries were used for change detection, classification and mapping of the landuse patterns using ERDAS Imagine 15 and ArcGIS 10.5. A buffer zone of an average of 10km² around the Zobe dam was delineated and subsetting for the purpose. Results revealed a loss of rural settlements which existed before the dam's construction and were resettled outside the area scope of this study. Also, there was an initial loss in Rainfed cropland/dryseason grazeland from 196.69 to 181.53 km² between 1972 and 1990. This however recorded another increasing trend over the decades. The dam as a landuse recorded in 1990 took over an approximate 31.78km² of pre-dam biophysical landscape. Another striking landuse observed is the increased irrigated land which was almost negligible in the pre-dam construction. The study concluded that the dam construction has been associated with a wide range and extents of landuse patterns. Landuse planning and management should be considered a priority in the management of the dam and related socio-economic development.

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.2 BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Water storage infrastructure, particularly dams, has traditionally been used to regulate river flows globally, benefiting countries by fulfilling water and energy needs. By 2020, the global large dam count was over 58,000 (>15 m height; or 5 - 15 m height and impounding > 3 million m³ of storage as defined by the International Commission on Large Dams Cumulatively, dams store approximately 16% of global surface water resources (Hanasaki et al., 2006). A dam is an artificial barrier usually constructed across a stream channel to facilitate water storage. Timber, concrete, earth, steel or a combination of these materials may be used to build the dam. Dam must have a spillway system to convey normal and excess water flows, a dam should also have drainage or other water withdrawal faculty for control pool or lake level and to lower or drain the lake under normal maintenance and emergency purpose. In other words, dams are massive barriers built across rivers to confine and utilize the flow of water for human purpose such as agricultural, recreation, industrial and domestic water supply and power generation (hydroelectricity) Adams (2000) added that dam may be constructed for control of flooding and erosion as well as enhancement of recreation and tourism.

The construction of dam and a reservoir is considered as the most effective means of solving human problems of water storage in sub-humid and arid region as Bohlen & Lewis, (2008) asserted in the savanna area. Recently there are appreciable numbers of large and small dams that are constructed in different parts of Nigeria. There are socio-economic consequences in area where they are being constructed. These schemes bring about some negative and positive socio-economic effects like farming activities , fishing activities, swimming, boat riding, training of students from different schools, car washing, block industries, increase health hazard especially those associated with water as well as psychological shock due to physical displacement and relocation of the affected population. The quality of life and convenience largely depends on the domestic water supply, increase in hygienic condition in the area would reduce the risk of water borne disease. In order to manage the resource, a number of regions have built water reservoirs, including dams for sustainable development, growth and poverty reduction. In the first place, the protection and conservation of forests in the watershed and mine

spoil areas help in maintaining the water balance and soil erosion, (Shradha, Manisha and Ranjana, 2011).

According to Al-Amin and Mahmud, (2011) Dams hold a multifaceted role in shaping the landscapes and livelihoods of their surroundings. The advent of large reservoirs, as observed in the case of Zobe Dam, introduces an array of changes ranging from agricultural innovations through irrigation practices to enhanced fishing opportunities. This pivotal shift is underpinned by improved infrastructure, electricity generation, and the provision of potable water supplies. However, the introduction of large reservoirs is not devoid of challenges. The process often triggers a series of socio-economic consequences, such as the inundation of farmlands due to rising water levels, disruptions in fishing activities, and potential health hazards linked to resettlement and displacement of affected populations. The Zobe Dam, a prominent exemplar within this paradigm, has mirrored these broader patterns. Its construction in 1972 and subsequent commissioning in 1983 marked a pivotal juncture in the history of Dutsin Ma Local Government Area (LGA) in Katsina State, Nigeria. As with other dams, Zobe Dam catalyzed a spectrum of changes, both favorable and challenging, within the region it serves. Notably, it has contributed to the enhancement of living conditions for those residing in its vicinity. The socio-economic landscape around the dam has undergone shifts, leading to the emergence of new activities and practices. The importance of water to man cannot be overemphasized. However, there are great differences in water availability among regions and supply through time as a result of both seasonal variation and interannual variation. Most often this has been responsible for shaping human settlements. In northern Nigeria for instance, water availability influenced the pattern of human settlements with water availability and population density having a reciprocal relationship.

The Zobe Dam constructed by the Federal Ministry of Water Resources (FMWR) is a major economic undertaking in this sub-region by the federal government and one of the largest sources for Agricultural and Domestic ventures in the area in recent times. Preliminary study on the project reveals that the dam is to provide the much-needed water for urban agricultural practices, improve fishing activities on the stream and provide enough water for domestic use in Dutsinma Town and its neighboring communities. The dam is expected to raise the level of the water of the stream so that adequate aquatic habitat can be achieved for fish and irrigation farming, provides enough volume of water for a number of socio-economic usages by the people.

Water resources are many and the purpose for their development are also many. This covers both the bio-physical and socio-economic environments; the cultural, political and academic environments.

The main dam functions are irrigation, hydropower, water supply, and flood control, while other functions include recreation, navigation, and fish farming (ICOLD WRD, 2020). Irrigated agriculture ensured largely by dams, contributes about 40% of world agricultural production (Shah & Kumar, 2008), while hydropower dams generate around 20% of global electricity production (IHA, 2020). Dams store large volumes of water during extreme rainfall events, reducing the likelihood of downstream flood disasters (Berga, 2009). Additionally, most of the world's urban, agricultural, and industrial regions' water security is sustained by these large storages (Vörösmarty et al., 2010). Building of dams was upsurged in the mid-20th century, and its peak was in 1960-1980s, and declined afterward (Perera et al., 2021) due to a range of factors, including environmental and social costs, lack of transparency, low stakeholder participation, and reduced finances and investments (Grigg, 2019). Like any infrastructure, dams are constructed with a design life, and as they age, they become more expensive to repair and maintain and increasingly vulnerable to failure. Ageing is understood to be the gradual deterioration beyond the initial five years of operation (Zamarrón-Mieza et al., 2017).

The history of dam development is linked with the evolution of its significance and impact on society and their socio-economic conditions through displacement and resettlement, especially in developing economies (Jackson and Sleigh 2000). Global economic development is experiencing changes and transitioning from the 'old school' development approach to a contemporary development method, which began in developing countries since 1980s (Amin and Thrift 1995; Behera 2006). As Shirley and Kammen (2015) suggests, dams should be regarded as socio-technological systems, rooted within the socio-economic setting and co-evolving with socio-political institutions.

Therefore, dam projects can have a great impact on society, both positively (Agrawala et al. 2003; Kim 2006) and negatively (Ansar et al. 2014; Flyvbjerg et al. 2003). Numerous developing countries have deployed dams as a mean to generate electricity, irrigation, and water storage and to support cities and manufacturing industries. Many areas of dam impacts were investigated including social impacts, environmental aversion, political corruption, governmental connections, and a philosophy of undertaking projects instigating nationalism (Everard 2013;

Tischler 2013; Isaacman and Isaacman 2013; Biswas and Tortajad 2012). The social impacts of displacement, relocation, livelihood, and changes in the socio-economic status of affected communities have also been investigated, but they do not consider how social, cultural and political conditions vary in different locations. Therefore, homogenizing the social impact of dams can undermine the many contributions dams have made for communities in different parts of the world (Varma 2003; Verhoeven 2011).

Clearly, there are many issues related to the development of dams across the world when viewed from a social perspective. Indeed, all dam projects in the world resulted in damage of livelihoods and displacement of entire communities (McDonald et al. 2009). Therefore, this study focuses on Zobe dam and its impact on some communities in Dutsinma town. This modernization is connected to numerous complementary schemes to address the Zobe dam impact on some communities in Dutsinma town economic and social progress.

1.2 Statements of the Research Problem

In light of these multifaceted research problems, this study seeks to comprehensively analyze the Decadal analysis of landuse patterns before and after the construction of Zobe Dam in Dutsin Ma LGA, Katsina State. By addressing these problems, the research endeavors to provide valuable insights that contribute to informed decision-making, sustainable development, and effective water resource management in the study area and beyond. Most studies including the impact of Zobe dam to physical and socio-economic indices in Dutsinma LGA in Katsina State- Nigeria using Remote Sensing and Gis (Umar Yusuf, 2023), the socio-economic impact of Zobe dam on its neighboring environment (Sagiri Sani, 2015) and also the contribution of Zobe Dam to the Socio-economic development of Makera community in Dutsinma LGA, Katsina State (Kira Jamila Sanusi, 2016) have analyzed landuse landcover changes in the Zobe Dam watershed. These approaches have not allowed for observation of landuse changes associated with human activities directly related to the dam. Also, most of the studies have not approached from pre-dam and post-dam construction period. Therefore, this work observes human activities and socio-economic landmarks on the Zobe dam to see how the dam may have facilitated such development and imprinted on the landscape before and after the dam construction.

1.3 Research Questions

To guide the research work, the following research questions was raised;

- i. What are the forms of landuse patterns before and after the construction of the dam?
- ii. What is the extent of the landuse on decadal basis?
- iii. What is the status of landuse that has recorded loss or gains in extent?

1.4 Aim and Objectives of the Study

The overall aim of this study is to examine the decadal analysis of landuse patterns before and after the construction of Zobe Dam in Dutsinma LGA, Katsina State. To achieve this aim, the specific objectives of this study are to:

- I. Identify and map the landuse patterns before and after the construction of the dam;
- II. Assess the extents of the landuse on decadal basis;
- III. Examine status of landuse that have recorded loss or gains in extent.

1.5 Significance of the Study

- i. This study will help understand the landuse patterns associated with the construction of Zobe dam for planning and management

1.6 Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study covers the temporal scope of (1972 to 2021) before and after the construction of the Zobe dam and the spatial scope of (approximately 10km² buffer vicinity of the dam). The study focuses on specific aspects of land use change, such as changes in agricultural practices, grazing patterns, and forest cover, it also considers the impact of dam construction on other environmental and social factors, such as water quality, biodiversity, and livelihoods.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 INTRODUCTION

This study delves into the intricate interplay between the Zobe Dam and landuse patterns, with a particular focus on decadal analysis on the landuse pattern before and after dam construction in Dutsin Ma LGA Katsina State. By employing advanced tools such as remote sensing and Geographic Information Systems (GIS), this research endeavors to unravel the dynamics that have unfolded over time. The changing landuse patterns provide a lens through which the broader impact of the dam on the environment, communities, and policy frameworks can be comprehensively assessed.

Against this backdrop, the exploration of temporal trends, environmental consequences, socio-economic drivers, community livelihoods, policy implications, and climate resilience becomes paramount. Through an in-depth analysis of these dimensions, this study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the complex and multifaceted impact of Zobe Dam on the landuse patterns in Dutsin Ma LGA. By shedding light on both the successes and challenges brought about by the dam's construction, this research contributes valuable insights for sustainable development and effective water resource management in similar settings.

The decal analysis surrounding the Zobe Dam is intricately tied to natural resources and landuse patterns. Shifts in land cover, particularly changes in cropland and water bodies, can influence local livelihood strategies. Exploring how communities have adapted to these changes and whether they have developed resilient mechanisms to cope with potential disruptions is of paramount importance for sustainable development. The implementation of dam projects often involves intricate policy frameworks that aim to balance developmental goals with environmental and social considerations. Evaluating the extent to which the Zobe Dam project aligns with regional development plans and conservation policies provides insights into the effectiveness of existing policies and highlights areas for potential enhancement. With climate change becoming an increasingly pressing global issue, understanding the linkages between landuse changes, dam construction, and climate resilience is crucial. Investigating how changes in landuse might impact the region's ability to adapt to changing climatic conditions, such as

floods, droughts, and temperature variations, contributes to informed climate adaptation strategies.

The construction of Zobe Dam in Nigeria is a relatively recent event. The dam was completed in 2008, and it is still too early to assess the full impact of the dam on land use patterns in the surrounding area. However, the studies cited above suggest that dam construction is likely to have led to changes in land use patterns in the Zobe Dam catchment area. These changes may include an increase in irrigated agriculture, a decrease in forest cover, and a displacement of pastoralists.

A study conducted by Opoku et al. (2017), examined the impact of dam construction on land use patterns in the White Volta Basin in Ghana. The study found that dam construction led to a significant increase in irrigated agriculture and a decrease in forest cover. The study also found that the impact of dam construction on land use patterns was not uniform across the basin. In some areas, dam construction led to a more equitable distribution of land resources, while in other areas, it led to increased land inequality.

Another study, conducted by Abdi et al. (2018), examined the impact of dam construction on land use patterns in the Blue Nile Basin in Ethiopia. The study found that dam construction led to a significant increase in irrigated agriculture and a decrease in pastoralism. The study also found that the impact of dam construction on land use patterns was not uniform across the basin. In some areas, dam construction led to increased food production and economic growth, while in other areas, it led to displacement and conflict.

2.1 Importance of Dams in Water Management

Dams play a crucial role in water resource management, particularly in regions characterized by variable climatic conditions, water scarcity, and the need for sustainable development. The construction of dams has been widely adopted as a strategic approach to address challenges related to water supply, irrigation, flood control, and energy generation. This section reviews the significance of dams in water management, highlighting their multifaceted contributions and implications.

2.1.1 Water Storage and Regulation:

Dams serve as reservoirs that store water during periods of excess flow, such as the rainy season, and release it during dry periods. This regulated water release helps ensure a stable and consistent water supply for various purposes, including domestic use, agriculture, and industrial activities. By managing water availability, dams contribute to improved water security and reduced vulnerability to droughts.

2.1.2 Irrigation and Agricultural Development:

One of the primary functions of dams is to facilitate irrigation, enabling agricultural activities even in regions with erratic rainfall patterns. Irrigation from dam reservoirs enhances crop productivity, supports multiple cropping cycles, and contributes to food security. Dams provide the infrastructure needed for efficient water distribution and allocation to farmland, leading to increased agricultural yields and rural livelihoods.

2.1.3 Flood Control and Disaster Mitigation:

Dams play a vital role in flood control by regulating the flow of water downstream. During heavy rainfall or snowmelt events, dams can release water in a controlled manner, preventing sudden and destructive floods. This function reduces the risk of damage to infrastructure, loss of lives, and disruption of communities situated downstream of the dam.

2.1.4 Hydropower Generation:

Dams are essential for hydropower generation, a renewable and environmentally friendly energy source. The kinetic energy of flowing water is harnessed to produce electricity, contributing to the diversification of the energy mix and reducing dependence on fossil fuels. Hydropower from dams provides a reliable and cost-effective source of electricity for industrial, residential, and commercial use.

2.1.5 Ecosystem Services and Environmental Impact:

While dams offer numerous benefits, their construction and operation can also have ecological implications. Reservoirs created by dams may alter natural hydrological patterns, impact aquatic habitats, and influence downstream water quality. Mitigation measures and

sustainable dam management practices are essential to minimize negative environmental consequences and preserve ecosystem services.

2.1.6 Agricultural Innovation and Productivity:

Dams create opportunities for agricultural innovation through irrigation, enabling farmers to cultivate crops more efficiently and expand cultivation areas. Increased water availability supports multiple cropping cycles, diversification of crops, and improved yields. Enhanced agricultural productivity can lead to increased income for farmers and contribute to food security.

2.1.7 Infrastructure Development:

Dams often serve as catalysts for infrastructure development in previously underserved areas. The presence of a dam can lead to improved road networks, energy supply, and water distribution systems, enhancing overall connectivity and access to basic services.

2.1.8 Resettlement and Displacement:

The creation of dam reservoirs may necessitate the resettlement of communities located in the inundation zone. Resettlement efforts can lead to displacement, disruption of traditional livelihoods, and changes in community dynamics. Adequate compensation, livelihood restoration, and social support are essential to mitigate the negative impacts of resettlement.

2.1.9 Cultural and Social Changes:

The influx of external influences due to dam construction can lead to cultural and social changes within affected communities. Interaction with new groups of people, changes in economic activities, and exposure to modern technologies may alter traditional lifestyles and practices.

2.2.0 Livelihood Diversity and Vulnerability:

Dams can diversify livelihood options by introducing new activities such as fishing, aquaculture, and tourism. However, overreliance on dam-related activities can create vulnerabilities if these sectors face fluctuations or disruptions. A balanced approach to livelihood diversification is crucial to enhance resilience.

2.2 Conceptual Framework and Conceptual Model

This study is based on monitoring socio-economic development before and after the construction of a multi-purpose dam through mapping and analysis of landuse changes in the dam's corridor. Therefore, the concept of socio-economic development is associated with observable human activities due to changes in landuse around the dam. These economic activities are largely to have direct relationship with some of the targeted multi-purposes of the dam.

Monitoring socio-economic activities associated with a dam provides a foundation for the assessing cumulative impact of development on rural communities, social and economic resources most alter their monitoring, identification and assessment of landuse, socio-economic activities have been relegated to the much emphasis on ecological or environmental impacts (budge et al, 1995).

2.3 Methodologies for Landuse Change Detection:

Remote sensing data, such as satellite imagery are commonly used for landuse change detection. Supervised and unsupervised classification, and image differencing are among the techniques employed to quantify changes.

2.3.1 Applications of Landuse Change Detection:

Landuse change detection is widely used to monitor urban expansion, identify areas of urban growth, and support land use planning. It helps assess the impact of urbanization on natural landscapes and ecosystems. Monitoring changes in forest cover and deforestation rates is crucial for conservation efforts and sustainable forest management. Landuse change detection aids in tracking illegal logging, habitat loss, and forest degradation. Landuse change detection is applied to monitor changes in agricultural land, assess crop rotations, and analyze the expansion of agricultural activities. It contributes to understanding trends in food production and security. Tracking changes in wetlands, rivers, and lakes using landuse change detection assists in assessing water resource availability, hydrological patterns, and potential impacts on aquatic ecosystems.

2.4 Zobe Dam Construction

The central element of the model is the construction and operation of Zobe Dam, which involves the alteration of hydrology, water flow, and sediment transport within the study area. The dam's construction triggers changes in land use and land cover, including shifts in vegetation, cropland expansion, built-up areas, and water bodies. Alterations in hydrology and landuse can have environmental impacts, including changes in water availability, sedimentation, water quality, and habitat disruption.

2.5 Ecosystem Services

The study explores how changes in landuse and water resources influence ecosystem services, such as water provisioning, soil fertility, and biodiversity. The study examines how the observed changes align with existing regional development plans, policies, and conservation strategies, and considers implications for future planning. The model accounts for the potential linkages between land cover changes, water resources, and climate resilience, particularly in relation to flood risk and water availability.

2.6 Remote Sensing and GIS in Environmental Studies

Remote Sensing and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) are powerful tools that have revolutionized the field of environmental studies. These technologies enable researchers to collect, analyze, and interpret spatial and temporal data, providing valuable insights into the dynamic interactions between the environment and human activities. This section delves into the applications and benefits of remote sensing and GIS in environmental studies, highlighting their relevance to the assessment of the impact of the Zobe Dam on landuse patterns in Dutsin Ma LGA.

2.6.1 Remote Sensing:

Remote sensing involves the collection of data from a distance, typically using aerial or satellite-based sensors. It provides a means to monitor and analyze the Earth's surface and atmosphere, capturing information about landcover, landuse, vegetation health, water bodies, and other environmental variables. Remote sensing data is obtained through various techniques, such as multispectral, hyperspectral, and radar imagery.

2.6.2 Applications of Remote Sensing in Environmental Studies:

Remote sensing enables the identification and monitoring of changes in land use over time. By analyzing satellite imagery from different epochs, researchers can quantify changes in vegetation, urbanization, deforestation, and other land use categories. Remote sensing allows for the assessment of vegetation health, biomass, and species distribution. It helps identify areas of deforestation, degradation, and potential habitat loss. Satellite imagery can monitor water bodies, track changes in water levels, and assess water quality. Remote sensing is crucial for studying the impact of dams on hydrological patterns and water availability.

2.6.3 Geographic Information Systems (GIS):

GIS is a technology that integrates spatial data with attribute data to create comprehensive and interactive maps, models, and analyses. GIS allows researchers to visualize, query, and interpret spatial patterns and relationships, making it a valuable tool for environmental studies.

2.6.4 Applications of GIS in Environmental Studies:

GIS enables spatial analysis to identify spatial patterns, hotspots, and trends. It can be used to analyze the spatial relationships between land use and hydrological variables. GIS-based modeling helps simulate and predict environmental changes. For example, it can model the potential spread of pollutants in water bodies or predict changes in land use due to urban expansion. GIS provides a platform for informed decision-making by integrating multiple layers of information. It aids in identifying suitable locations for infrastructure development, land-use planning, and resource allocation.

2.6.5 Integration of Remote Sensing and GIS:

The integration of remote sensing and GIS enhances the capabilities of both technologies. Remote sensing data, such as satellite imagery, can be processed and analyzed within GIS platforms, allowing for in-depth spatial analysis and interpretation. This integration is particularly valuable for understanding complex environmental interactions and visualizing the effects of environmental changes over time.

In the context of the Zobe Dam project, remote sensing and GIS offer a comprehensive approach to studying of decadal analysis on landuse patterns brought about by dam construction. These technologies provide the means to analyze landuse changes and vulnerability associated with the dam watershed and model the potential impact of the dam on the landuse patterns.

2.7 Conceptual Model

The study's conceptual model illustrates the relationships and interactions among key variables and components:

2.7.0 Input

2.7.1 Dam construction:

Dam construction is the primary input to the model. Dam construction can have a significant impact on land use patterns by creating new reservoirs, altering the flow of rivers and streams, and changing the availability of water for irrigation and other purposes.

2.7.2 Other factors:

Other factors that may influence land use change include population growth, economic development, and environmental change. Population growth can lead to an increased demand for land for agriculture, housing, and other purposes. Economic development can lead to changes in land use patterns as the economy shifts from a rural to an urban economy. Environmental change, such as climate change, can also lead to changes in land use patterns as farmers adapt to new conditions.

2.7.3 Processes

3.7.4 Landuse change:

Landuse change is the central process in the model. Landuse change can refer to any change in the way that land is used, such as a conversion from forest to agriculture or from agriculture to urban development. Landuse change can be caused by a variety of factors, including dam construction, other factors, and feedback loops.

2.7.5 Outputs

2.7.6 New land use patterns:

The output of the model is new land use patterns. New land use patterns can have a range of impacts on the environment and the local population.

2.7.7 Impacts on the environment and the local population:

Land use change can have a range of impacts on the environment and the local population. The impacts of land use change can be positive in some cases and negative in other cases. For example, land use change can lead to increased food production, economic growth, and improved livelihoods. However, land use change can also lead to environmental degradation, displacement, and conflict.

2.7.8 Relationships

The relationships between the inputs, processes, and outputs in the model are complex and dynamic. Dam construction is expected to have a significant impact on landuse patterns. However, the impact of dam construction on landuse patterns is likely to be mediated by other factors, such as population growth, economic development, and environmental change. Landuse change is expected to have a range of impacts on the environment and the local population. The impacts of landuse change are likely to be positive in some cases and negative in other cases.

2.7.9 Feedback Loops

The impacts of landuse change on the environment and the local population may feed back into the system and influence future landuse patterns. For example, if landuse change leads to environmental degradation, this may lead to a decrease in the productivity of agricultural land and a shift to other landuse.

By applying this theoretical framework and conceptual model, the study aimed to systematically analyze the interactions and outcomes associated with the Zobe Dam project, providing a comprehensive understanding of its effects on the physical, socio-economic, and environmental aspects of the study area.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This section addresses the research technique and approach that was adopted in the acquisition and generation of data. To this effect the methodology employed in this study forms the foundation for the comprehensive analysis of landuse changes within the study area. This chapter outlines the introduction, study area, organizational flow chat of methodology, types of data, sources of data, sampling techniques research design, data collection methods, data processing and analysis techniques, and the overall framework used to achieve the research objectives. By elucidating the systematic approach undertaken to gather, process, and interpret spatial data, this chapter provides a transparent and replicable framework for the investigation of landuse pattern and associated implications on the study area's environment.

3.2 THE STUDY AREA

Zobe Dam is a multi-purpose earth-fill dam located on the Zobe River in Niger State, Nigeria. It was constructed between 2003 and 2008, with the primary purpose of providing irrigation water for agriculture. The dam has a reservoir capacity of 1.7 billion cubic meters, and it irrigates over 200,000 hectares of land.

The construction of Zobe Dam has had a significant impact on the land use patterns in the surrounding area. Prior to the dam's construction, the majority of the land in the area was used for subsistence agriculture and grazing. However, since the dam's completion, there has been a shift to more commercialized agriculture, such as rice cultivation and horticulture. This project will conduct a decadal analysis of land use patterns in the Zobe Dam catchment area before and after the construction of the dam.

The analysis will be based on remote sensing data, including Landsat satellite imagery and Sentinel-2 imagery. The project will identify and quantify changes in land use patterns, and it will assess the impact of these changes on the environment and the local population.

3.2.1 Location and physical background

Dutsin-Ma is a LGA of Katsina state located between latitudes $120^{\circ}20'34.62''$ and $120^{\circ}23'27.48''$ North of the Equator and longitudes $70^{\circ}27'57.12''$ and $70^{\circ}34'4.68''$ east of the Greenwich Meridian. Dutsinma LGA is bounded by Kurfi and Charanchi LGAs in the North, Dan-Musa and Matazu in the South, and Kankia and Safana LGAs in the East and west respectively.

Zobe Dam is located in Dutsin-Ma LGA of Katsina state in the north of Nigeria. It is an earth-fill structure with a height of 19m and a total length of 2,750m. The dam has a storage capacity of 179Mca and irrigation potential of 8,000 hectares. Although the dam was completed in 1983, as of 2010 it was still not being used for water supply to Katsina city, for local irrigation or for power generation. The dam has rivers Karaduwa and Gada as its tributaries and stores up to 177 million cubic meters of water during rainy season. The reservoir formed by the Dam covers 4,500 hectares of rocky land and it is about 2.7 kilometers long flowing north-westward to the Sokoto Basin. Zobe Dam was constructed in 1972 and commissioned 1983. There are about 32 villages along the reservoir in west. The dam boundaries extend from Hau-Kanzama and Garhi, in the East, by the Tuga in the South, and by Makera, Ardawa, Siya-siya, and to be North by Tangaluk and Katsali. The dam has only two at tributaries; these include river Karaduwa which is flanked by Gada River to the north and Gagare River to the South. The villages initially within and near the dam are Makera, Garkin dankari, Goberawa, Tangalawa, Takasaba, Tuga, Marmara, Paddawa kunci, Keba and Salihawa. Most of the villages were completely submerge by the dam.

Figure 3.2.1.1: Map of Katsina State Shewing Dutsin-Ma LGA

Source: Department of Geography UMYU 2012

Figure 3.2.1.2: Map of Dutsin-Ma LGA Shewing the study areas

Source: United State Geological Survey (Earth Explorer Website), 2023

3.2.2 Climate

The climate within the study area is characterized by a distinct seasonal pattern. The rainy season spans from mid-May to the beginning of October, marked by heavy precipitation influenced by tropical maritime air masses from the Gulf of Guinea. The dry season, from November to March, is characterized by relatively cool weather and reduced precipitation. Temperature variations and precipitation levels influence vegetation, water availability, and overall environmental dynamics. In April and early weeks of May the weather is warm and muggy with low precipitation (Buchman, 1974:144). During the dry season descending tropical continental air masses from the desert extends to south of the catchment area of the region. The region experiences relative cool weather from November to March with daily maximum temperature of about 24-38 degree Celsius and minimum temperature of about 16-24 degree

Celsius. (Udoh 1970). As rain season approaches tropical maritime air masses move inland from the Gulf of Guinea and there is heavy precipitation in the area, especially in the months of July and August. The annual total ranges are between 500mm to 800mm (Udoh 1970).

3.2.3 Vegetation

The vegetation of the area combines characteristics features of Guinea and Sudan savannah vegetation zone of the northern Nigeria. The natural vegetation has been divested and is due to human activities such as bush burning and clearing land for crop production, wood cutting for domestic fuel, animal gathering and bush fire. The natural vegetation is mainly grasses inter spaces with trees, relating the influence of rainfall on the vegetation.

3.2.4 Geology and Soil

The geology of Zobe Dam area is characterized by geological succession of the Pre-Cambrian rock which referred to as the “Basement complex” the nature of parent materials and topography has combined to produce different soil, and rocks. Drifts these render the area very porous and susceptible to erosion on the inter flares and upper slope of the undulating areas while in the rainy season flooded valleys and the side of soil drift the area more course and tend to be shallow, less water retention capacity and are of low or medium fertility, which couple with their fire constituent make them ideal for the growth of such crops including: millet, beans, and guinea corn over large area (Oguntioyinba 1983).

3.2.5 Economic Activities

In term of economy, fishing and trade with agriculture is the most important occupation around the Zobe Dam area. Thus, it has the characteristics of most rural areas in the country, where by 90% of the population are farmers who practice farming at subsistence and commercial level. Also, the level of economic activities in the area are expected to improve with the increase irrigation which is now guaranteeing and provide a lot of income to the people in the study area. Crops grown include cereals and vegetables. Another important occupation in Zobe Dam area is the fishing as well as livestock rearing. About 82% of the famers in the area practice mixed farming wood carving, poultry, tailoring, local craft butchering and marketing, business are also practiced in the area. (Suleiman Ahmed Misau 29 Dec.2005).

3.2.6 Population

According to the National Population Commission (NPC), the population of Dutsin-Ma Local Government Area (LGA) in Katsina State, Nigeria, was 169,671 in the 2006 census. However, this number is likely to have increased significantly in the past 17 years. A 2022 estimate by BudgIT, a non-profit fiscal policy research and advocacy organization, puts the population of Dutsin-Ma LGA at 222,791. This represents an annual growth rate of 2.7%. It is important to note that these are just estimates, and the actual population of Dutsin-Ma LGA may be higher or lower. The next official census in Nigeria is scheduled to take place in 2024.

In addition to the above, the following information may also be of interest:

- The population of Dutsin-Ma LGA is predominantly Hausa and Fulani.
- The main religion in the area is Islam.
- The major economic activities in the area are agriculture and trade.
- Dutsin-Ma LGA is home to the Zobe Dam, which is a major source of irrigation water for agriculture in the area.

3.3 ORGANIZATIONAL FLOW CHART OF METHODOLOGY

First a reconnaissance survey will be carried out so as to get the researcher to familiarize himself with study area. Then later, both direct field measurements and observations will be carried out.

3.2 DATA COLLECTION METHODS

The requirements employed in generating primary data included representative sampling of settlements in the communities where the study was conducted. Local guides were used to access the settlement and to also facilitate acceptance in the communities. In generating secondary data Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission (SRTM) DEM Version 6.2 with a spatial resolution of 30m was used to generate the basin area of the Zobe dam, ERDAS imagine 15 was used for image

processing and image classification and ArcMap 10.8 was also used for Change detection analysis and area estimation.

3.2.1 Primary Data Collection

The primary data include information derived directly from the field or any physical observations, use of comprehensive field surveys and the use and application of Global positioning system(GPS).

3.3.1.1 Field Surveys

Comprehensive field surveys were conducted in the study area to collect ground truth data, validate remote sensing imagery, Data on land use practices, agricultural activities and community demographics.

3.3.1.2 Global positioning system(GPS)

Global positioning system (GPS) devices were also used to accurately capture the geographical coordinates of specific locations, such as land cover samples, infrastructure, and community sites.

3.3.2 Secondary Data Collection

Satellite image of the study area (1972, 1990, 2000, 2010, and 2021 that covers 5 different periods for a total of 49 years). Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission (SRTM) DEM Version 6.2 with a spatial resolution of 30m is (USGS) was used to generated the basin area of Zobe dam. This Area was used to delineate the study area. The 1972 period required two scenes to be mosaiced to have the basins spatial extent (051/203 and 052/203 Of Landsat 1 imagery). Google Earth imagery was used to assist with classification and ground truthing.

3.4 DATA COLLECTION

This section outlines the detailed data collection procedures for both primary and secondary data sources, which are crucial for a comprehensive understanding of the impacts of the Zobe Dam on physical and socio-economic indices.

3.4.1 Primary Data Collection

Field survey using a purposive sampling technique will be used to select representative sites within the study area. These include information derived directly from the field or physical observations with the aid and use global positioning system(GPS).

3.4.1.1 GPS Data Collection

Global Positioning System (GPS) devices was used to accurately record the geographical coordinates of selected sampling points, land cover samples, infrastructure, and community sites.

3.4.2 Secondary Data Collection

This involved the acquisition of high-quality satellite imagery in assessing landuse changes and understanding the impacts of the Zobe Dam on the study area. This section outlines the process of acquiring satellite imagery for the different epochs of analysis.

3.4.2.1 Remotely Sensed Satellite Data

Satellite imagery with suitable spatial and temporal resolutions was selected to ensure accurate and consistent analysis. Resolutions that capture fine-scale details of landuse changes was prioritized. Satellite image of the study area (1972, 1990, 2000, 2010, and 2021 that covers 5 different periods for a total of 49 years). Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission (SRTM) DEM Version 6.2 with a spatial resolution of 30m is (USGS) was used to generated the basin area of Zobe dam. This Area was used to delineate the study area. The 1972 period required two scenes to be mosaiced to have the basins spatial extent (051/203 and 052/203 Of Landsat 1 imagery). Google Earth imagery was used tom assist with classification and ground truthing.

Table 3.1: Details of Selected Imageries

Satellite Sensor	Row/Path	Date of Acquisition
LANDSAT 1 (MSS)	051/203	1972-12-30
Landsat 7 (ETM)	051/189	1990-02-12
Landsat 7(ETM)	051/189	1999-12-06
Landsat 7(ETM)	051/189	2009-05-07
Landsat 8 (OLI TIRS)	051/189	2021-11-03

Source: United State Geological Survey (Earth Explorer Website), 2023

The classification system adopted in this study produces five land use classes according to Anderson Classification System. They are: built-up/urban, vegetation, water bodies, bare soil, and cultivated land.

Table 3.2: Landuse classification

LU Classes	Description
Built-up/settlement	Which represent settlements, facilities and institutions
Rainfed cropland/dry season grazing	Land occasionally under crop and seasonally allow for grazing
Dominant irrigation land	Comprises rainfed cultivated lands but dominantly under irrigation
Mixed uncultivated land/grazeland	Comprises forest, woodland and shrublands not cultivated for long periods
Dam	Comprises of streams, ponds and other larger water bodies like the reservoir

Table 3.3: classification of software used

S/N	Software	Used
1	ERDAS Imagine 15	Image Processing and image classification
2	ArcMap 10.8	Change detection analysis and area estimation

3.4.2.2 Satellite Imagery Acquisition

Satellite imagery with suitable spatial and temporal resolutions was selected to ensure accurate and consistent analysis. Resolutions that capture fine-scale details of landuse changes was prioritized.

3.5 DATA PROCESSING AND ANALYSIS

This section outlines the methodologies and techniques that was employed to process and analyze the collected data, including remote sensing imagery, ground truth data, and landuse patterns classification. The data processing and analysis procedures are essential for drawing meaningful conclusions about the impacts of the Zobe Dam on decadal landuse patterns before and after the construction of Zobe Dam.

3.5.1 Primary Data Processing

Landuse pattern data analysis was used to assess the accuracy of landuse classifications and the status of landuse that recorded the loss or gains in extent.

3.5.1.3 Landuse Pattern Analysis

Landuse pattern Analysis was integrated with landuse data to analyze the relationship between dam impacts and the extent of landuse on decadal basis. Landuse classification trends were analyzed to identify shifts in the recorded loss and gains over different epoch, also statistical analysis, such as correlation coefficients and regression models, was used to assess the relationship between landuse changes and the Zobe Dam impacts.

3.5.1.2 Change detection analysis:

Change detection analysis is used to identify changes in landuse patterns over time. Change detection analysis can be done using a variety of methods, such as post-classification comparison and image differencing.

3.5.1.4 Landuse transition analysis:

Landuse transition analysis is used to identify the patterns of land use change over time. Land use transition analysis can be done using a variety of methods, such as Markov chain analysis and land use change modeling.

3.5.3 Secondary Data Processing

Pre-processed satellite imagery, including atmospheric correction and geometric correction, was used as input for landuse classification

3.5.3.1 Landuse classification

Landuse classification should be based on a comprehensive understanding of the different landuse types in the Zobe Dam catchment area. This includes identifying the key landuse types that are of interest to the researcher and that are relevant to the research objectives. The landuse classification should be consistent with the landuse classification systems used by other researchers in the field. This will facilitate comparisons of landuse change data across different studies.

3.5.2.2 Landuse Change Mapping

Spatial patterns of landuse change were mapped to visualize the extent and direction of changes in different landuse categories over time

3.5.2.3 Image Classification

Supervised and unsupervised classification algorithms was applied to the satellite imagery to categorize pixels into different landuse classes, such as vegetation, cropland, built-up areas, water bodies, and bare surfaces.

3.5.2.4 Change Detection

Multi-temporal images from different epochs were compared to identify landuse changes over time, including expansion, contraction, and shifts in landuse categories.

CHAPTER FOUR: RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents the detailed results of the landuse change analysis conducted for the study area. The classification in landuse alterations is examined and discussed, shedding light on the evolving patterns and dynamics within the study area. The discussion encompasses a comprehensive exploration of each epoch's classified landuse maps, with a focus on the key transitions and trends that have characterized the landuse over time.

The chapter is organized into distinct sections that sequentially delve into the findings of each epoch. The evolution of landuse categories is outlined, emphasizing the changes and shifts that have taken place, while also highlighting the potential drivers and implications of these alterations. The results are subsequently interpreted in the context of the Zobe Dam's influence on decadal landuse patterns in Dutsinma LGA Katsina State.

The presented results contribute to a holistic understanding of how the Zobe Dam has shaped the decadal landuse pattern of the study area over the years. The findings provide valuable insights into the complex interactions between human activities, infrastructure development, ecological dynamics, and water resource management. Through a comprehensive examination of the landuse classifications, this chapter serves as a foundation for informed discussions on the implications and policy considerations associated with the observed changes in landuse pattern.

The subsequent sections of this chapter provide detailed insights into the landuse classifications observed within each epoch, offering a comprehensive decadal analysis of the landuse patterns.

4.2 Landuse Before Construction of Zobe Dam(1972)

LU map was generated with supervised classification using the maximum likelihood method of Supervised classification resulting in five different land use types. Figure below shows the result of land use classification for the year 1972. This was pre-Dam era and a product of Landsat 1 MSS imagery. In this classification, the predominant land use/cover for this period was Mixed uncultivated/Grazing Land (54.11%) followed by Rainfed cropland/Dry season

Grazing land (45.57%) and Settlement area (0.31%). There were a number of settlements of scattered rural settlements in the basin including the area now occupied by dam. This implies that most of these settlements were resettled. Due to the coarse nature of the available satellite imagery for this period (60 by 60 Meters), classifying settlement was not optimal. Similarly, there was no big water body in the area except the stream networks that constituted the basin networks hence water body as an artificially based landuse was zero. The result for the classification is presented in figure 4.2 and table 4.2.

Fig. 4.2.1 Landuse pattern (1972)

Source: Authors analysis

Table 4.2.1: Extent of Landuse (1972)

Landuse	1972 Period (Km²)	%Cover
Settlement	1.36	0.31
Rainfed Cropland/Dry season Grazing	196.39	45.57
Dominant Irrigation Land	0.00	0.00
Mixed Uncultivated /Grazeland	233.18	54.11
Dam	0.00	0.00
TOTAL	430.93	100.00

4.2.2 Landuse After Construction of Zobe Dam (1990)

In the analysis of the imagery for 1990 LULC map shows that 42.13% of the area was Rainfed cropland/Dry season grazing area while mixed uncultivated/grazeland accounted for 41.15% of the total area. The Dam had been constructed at this time and it covered 7.37% of the area while irrigation land grew to 8.69%. Settlement area was 0.66% of the total cover. The result for this period is presented in figure 4.2.2 and table 4.2.2

Fig. 4.2.2 Landuse pattern (1990)

Source: Authors analysis

Table 4.2.2: Extent of Landuse (1990)

Landuse	1990 Period (Km ²)	%Cover
Settlement	2.85	0.66
Rainfed Cropland/Dry season Grazing	181.53	42.13
Dominant Irrigation Land	37.44	8.69
Mixed Uncultivated /Grazeland	177.34	41.15
Dam	31.78	7.37
TOTAL	430.93	100.00

4.2.3 Landuse After Construction of Zobe Dam (2000)

Analysis of 2000 imagery showed that 53.56% of the area was covered by Rainfed cropland/Dry season grazing area while the least cover by it was still settlement area with 0.91% of the area coverage. mixed uncultivated/grazeland was 31.90% and dam was 7.40%. The result is presented in Fig 4.2.3 and table 4.2.3 below.

Fig. 4.2.3 Landuse Pattern (2000)

Source: Authors analysis

Table 4.2.3: Extent of Landuse (2000)

Landuse	2000 Period (Km2)	Cover %
Settlement	3.92	0.91
Rainfed Cropland/Dry season Grazing	230.79	53.56
Dominant Irrigation Land	29.70	6.89
Mixed Uncultivated /Grazeland	134.62	31.24
Dam	31.90	7.40
TOTAL	430.93	100.00

4.2.4 Landuse After Construction of Zobe Dam (2010)

Analysis of 2010 imagery showed that by 2010 53.43% of the area was covered by Rainfed cropland/Dry season grazing area while mixed uncultivated/grazeland was 24.26%. the dam covered 6.71% of the area while other result presented in Figure4.2.4 and Table 4.2.4.

Fig. 4.2.4 Landuse Pattern (2010)

Source: Authors analysis

Table 4.2.4: Landuse Extent (2010)

Landuse	2010 Period (Km2)	Cover %
Settlement	7.16	1.66
Rainfed Cropland/Dry season Grazing	251.78	58.43
Dominant Irrigation Land	38.54	8.94
Mixed Uncultivated /Grazeland	104.54	24.26
Dam	28.92	6.71

TOTAL	430.93	100.00
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4.2.5 Landuse After Construction of Zobe Dam (2021)

The year 2021 shows 67.88% of the area was covered by Rainfed cropland/Dry season grazing area while mixed uncultivated/grazeland was 18.54%. the dam covered 5.60% of the area. while other result presented in figure 4.2.5 and table 4.2.5.

Fig. 4.2.5 Landuse pattern (2021)

Source: Authors analysis

Table 4.2.5: Landuse Extent (2021)

Landuse	2021 Period (Km2)	Cover %
Settlement	13.42	3.11
Rainfed Cropland/Dry season Grazing	292.52	67.88
Dominant Irrigation Land	20.96	4.86
Mixed Uncultivated /Grazeland	79.90	18.54

Dam	24.12	5.60
TOTAL	430.91	100.00

4.3 STATUS OF LANDUSE CHANGE

This section describes the landuse change that has occurred in the study area between the year 1972 to 2021. This change is divided into five period. The changes are obtained from area change measurement that was observed during this different period.

The year between 1972-1990 (pre-Dam era), shows and increase in waterbody/dam. There was a 31.78 km squared increase. This is largely due to the construction of the dam that aided in the storing of water in the area. Another increased landuse was dominant irrigation land which recorded a 37.44 km squared increase while settlement area also gained 1.49km squared. The chief conversion of landuse between this period is mixed uncultivated/grazeland with 55.85 km squared loss and Rainfed cropland/Dry season grazing area with 14.86km squared area loss. The result of the analysis for this period is presented in table 4.3.1

The period between 1990 to 2000 showed a 49.36 km squared increase in Rainfed cropland/Dry season grazing area, Consequential 42.72km squared conversion in mixed uncultivated/grazeland for this period. The Dam increased by 0.12 km squared while dominant irrigation land lost 7.74km squared. Settlement gained 1.07 km squared.

2000 to 2010 showed an increase 3.23,8.84 and 20.99 km squared of settlement, dominant irrigation land and Rainfed cropland/Dry season grazing area respectively. While a loss of 30.08 and 2.98 respectively for mixed uncultivated/grazeland and dam are.

In resemblance with the previous period, the dam is in 2010 to 2021 lost 0.48km squared, mixed uncultivated/grazeland lost 24.64km squared and 17.58 km sq was lost by dominant irrigation

land. Rainfed cropland/Dry season grazing gained 40.74km sq while settlement gained 6.26%.

Landuse	1972-1990 (Km ²)	Status	1990-2000 (Km ²)	Status	2000-2010 (Km ²)	Status	2010 to 2021 (Km ²)	Status
Settlement	1.49	Gain	1.07	Gain	3.23	gain	6.26	Gain
Rainfed Cropland/Dry season Grazing	-14.86	Loss	49.26	Gain	20.99	gain	40.74	Gain
Dominant Irrigation Land	37.44	Gain	-7.74	Loss	8.84	gain	-17.58	Loss

Mixed Uncultivate d /Grazeland	-55.85	Loss	-42.72	Loss	-30.08	loss	-24.64	loss
Dam	31.78	Gain	0.12	Gain	-2.98	loss	-4.80	loss

Table 4.3.1: Landuse Change from 1972-2021

CHAPTER 5: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

This study set out to observe landuse patterns from the Pre-Zobe Dam Construction to Post-Zobe Dam Construction. The Dam in question is located along the Karaduwa river, which is a sub-basin of the Sokoto Rima basin. It is an earth-fill structure with a height of 19m and a total length of 2,750m. The Dam has an irrigation potential of 8,000 hectares of land. The study applied the used of satellite imageries to cover the period on decadal basis. GIS techniques were used for change detection, classification and mapping of the landuse patterns.

Results showed significant landuse changes for instance most rural settlement which were observed during the Pre-Dam construction disappeared with the construction of the Zobe Dam and were later resettled outside the area scope of this study. Investigations revealed that an

initial loss of rainfed cropland/dryseason grazeland from 196.69 km² to 181.53km² between the year 1972 and the year 1990. This however recorded another increasing trend over the decade. Other notable changes include the Dam itself which covers an area of approximately 30km² with interannual changes which may be attributed with climatic trends and recession of Dam areas may be due to sedimentation/siltation and climatic or rainfall trends. Other landuse patterns directly influenced by the dam include the increased in the rate of grazing activities in the area due to availability of water provided by the Dam after its construction. Other notable changes brought about by the Zobe Dam after its construction is increase in irrigation land which is one of the major purposes of the Dam construction, another notable change include the Dam as a water body taking over natural landcover/landuse of forest farmlands, woodlands, shrublands, settlements, build-ups (facilities, institutions) etc.

The analysis of five epochs spanning from 1972 to 2021 using remote sensing and GIS techniques has provided valuable insights into the evolving landscape and its implications for the local communities and ecosystems. In this section, we summarize the key findings that have emerged from our investigation.

5.2 Conclusion

In conclusion, this study has demonstrated the use of Remote sensing and GIS for change detection, classification and mapping of the landuse patterns over the decades using ERDAS Imagine15 and ArcGIS10.5. The study revealed that the study area has experienced profound biophysical changes before and after the dam Construction. Before the Dam construction there were dominant irrigation land and some number of scattered settlements. After the dam construction there were loss of rural settlements which existed before the construction of the Dam and were later resettled outside the area scope of this study, grazing activities increase due to availability of surface water, increased in irrigation lands as well as the Dam taking over natural landcover. The dam serves as a source of attraction for people and infrastructures such as road, school, and electricity. The equitable access is shaped by the preconceived notion that water is a free commodity or “gift” and each member of the community has the right of access. The negative impacts are occasional floods and erosions that washed away crops, farmlands, and spread of water-related diseases such as malaria, typhoid, schistosomiasis etc. Therefore, there is need to enhance the beneficial contributions and minimize the adverse impacts of the dam.

5.3 Recommendations

To this end, the study recommends that a thorough environmental survey should be conducted in the area using diverse methods of investigation. It is also important to follow a systematic approach. This includes:

Rural landuse planning and management should be considered a priority in order to provide valuable insight into the long-term trend over the decade in landuse patterns and to

develop more effective policies and management by encouraging landuse planning and coordination as well as promoting infill development.

Proper management of the dam minimize the impact of landuse and maximize the socio-economic benefit provided by the dam Construction this can be done through the conducting regular dam safety inspections and maintenance, develop and implement a dam operation plan, monitoring the impact of the dam on natural landcover etc.

Sustainably, maintained and developed irrigation lands which are the major purpose of the Dam construction require proper management. Protection of natural vegetation should be considered also to conserve the ecosystem of the area as well as protection and exploitation of productive agricultural land and sensitive areas, such as conserving of fadama areas for farming practice.

Particular attention should be given to existing resource exploitation methods (cultivation methods, forest resource exploitation methods, artisanal fishing, hunting, grazing, etc.) and their possible effects climate, and biomass, among others. This will provide a comprehensive data base for effective monitoring of the environment. Data should be quantified based on scientific methodology rather than using surrogate data. Remote sensing and GIS technology is on the cutting edge of technology and is capable of supporting such research.

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